

An updated checklist of Silverfish fauna (Insecta: Apterygota: Zygentoma) of India

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Abstract

An updated checklist of *Zygentoma* fauna from India is provided herewith. Altogether 22 species under 15 genera grouped in two families with their distribution records in India plus 2 species inquirenda are listed.

Keywords: *Silverfish, Zygentoma, Checklist, Lepisma, India.*

Received: 6 February 2020; Revised: 30 December 2020; Online: 31 December 2020

Introduction

The order *Zygentoma* (commonly known as silverfish), represent one of the earliest insect. They are considered to be the sister group of the winged insects (Blanke *et al.*, 2014). The name *Zygentoma* Börner, 1904 is used at present by all the taxonomists working on this group. The name “Thysanura” was originally created for an order that included, the *Zygentoma*, the *Microcoryphia*, the *Diplura* at different times, and even the *Collembola* (Gaju-Ricart *et al.*, 2015). The first silverfish described, was the European lepismatid household pest *Lepisma saccharina* Linnaeus, 1758. Gervais (1844) described the first soil-dwelling Nicoletiid, *Nicoletia phytophila*, considering its elongate form, without scales and eyes. So far, 625 species have been described worldwide under 5 families with 148 genera (Smith, 2018).

Escherich (1903) described the first Indian Lepismatid *Lepisma indica* from Matheran, Maharashtra, later Mendes (1988) have considered this as species inquirenda. Another species *Lepisma devadasi* Sukumar & Livingstone, 1993 has also been considered as species inquirenda (Smith, 2018). Escherich (1905, 1906), Silvestri (1913, 1935, 1938), Paclt (1961, 1967), Joseph & Mathad (1963), Hazra (1980, 1993, 1996, 2000, 2004, 2012), Mendes (1989, 1992), Hazra and Mandal (2004a, b & 2010) contributed to the knowledge of Indian *Zygentoma*. Subsequently

Hazra and Mandal (2007) published a pictorial handbook of Indian Thysanura. Mandal (2010) published a check list of Indian Thysanura.

The poorly known Indian fauna of *Zygentoma* is represented by 22 species under 2 families with 15 genera within which the family Lepismatidae represents a total of 12 species belonging to 8 genera plus 2 species inquirenda. The aim of the present communication is to provide an up to date list of *Zygentoma* fauna of India with distribution records.

Updated Checklist of *Zygentoma* from India

The detail updated checklist is provided herewith. Distribution records of species are based on published work of earlier authors.

Class Insecta

Order *Zygentoma* Börner, 1904

Family Lepismatidae (Latreille, 1802)

Subfamily Acrotelsatinae Mendes, 1991

Genus *Acrotelsa* Escherich, 1905

1. *Acrotelsa collaris* (Fabricius, 1793)

Distribution: Andhra Pradesh, Uttarakhand, West Bengal

Subfamily Ctenolepismatinae Mendes, 1991

Genus *Acrotelsella* Silvestri, 1935

2. *Acrotelsella wygodzinsky* (Hazra, 1980)

Distribution: West Bengal

Genus *Ctenolepisma* Escherich, 1905

Subgenus *Ctenolepisma* Escherich, 1905

3. *Ctenolepisma (Ctenolepisma) alticola* Silvestri, 1935

Distribution: Jharkhand, Ladakh

4. *Ctenolepisma (Ctenolepisma) boettgerianum* Paclt, 1961

Distribution: Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra

5. *Ctenolepisma (Ctenolepisma) longicaudatum* Escherich, 1905

Distribution: Andaman & Nicobar Island, Andhra Pradesh, Manipur, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Tripura, West Bengal

6. *Ctenolepisma (Ctenolepisma) nigra* (Oudemans, 1890)

Distribution: West Bengal

7. *Ctenolepisma (Ctenolepisma) tripurensis* Hazra, Biswas & Mitra, 2000

Distribution: Tripura

Genus *Thermobia* Bergroth, 1890

8. *Thermobia domestica* (Packard, 1873)

Distribution: Mandapam (Tamil Nadu)

Subfamily Lepismatinae (Latreille, 1802)

Genus *Afrolepisma* Mendes, 1981

9. *Afrolepisma nigrina* (Silvestri, 1913)

Distribution: Odisha

Genus *Lepisma* Linnaeus, 1758

10. *Lepisma saccharina* Linnaeus, 1758

Distribution: Sikkim, Uttarakhand

Genus *Tricholepisma* Paclt, 1967

11. *Tricholepisma gravelyi* (Silvestri, 1913)

Distribution: West Bengal

Genus *Xenolepisma* Mendes, 1981

12. *Xenolepisma subnigrina* (Silvestri, 1938)

Distribution: Tamil Nadu

Family Nicoletiidae (Lubbock, 1873)

Subfamily Atelurinae Remington, 1954

Tribe Atelurini Remington, 1954

Genus *Assmuthia* Escherich, 1906

13. *Assmuthia inermis* Escherich, 1906

Distribution: Maharashtra

14. *Assmuthia spinosissima* Escherich, 1906

Distribution: Maharashtra

Genus *Atelurodes* Silvestri, 1916

15. *Atelurodes typhloponis* (Silvestri, 1913)

Distribution: Uttarakhand, West Bengal

Genus *Bharatatelura* Mendes, 1992

16. *Bharatatelura malabarica* Mendes, 1992

Distribution: Goa, Haryana, Delhi, Maharashtra.

Genus *Neatelura* Joseph & Mathad, 1963

17. *Neatelura yellapurensis* Joseph & Mathad, 1963

Distribution: Karnataka

Genus *Platystylea* Escherich, 1906

18. *Platystylea barbifer* Escherich, 1906

Distribution: Maharashtra)

Tribe Atopatelurini Mendes, 2012

Genus *Pseudogastrotheus* Mendes, 2003

19. *Pseudogastrotheus indicus* (Silvestri, 1913)

Distribution: Odisha, Karnataka

20. *Pseudogastrotheus palpiseta* (Silvestri, 1916)

Distribution: Karnataka

Subfamily Coletiniinae Mendes, 1988

Genus *Lepidospora* Escherich, 1905

Subgenus *Lepidospora* Escherich, 1905

21. *Lepidospora (Lepidospora) ceylonica* Silvestri, 1911

Distribution: Uttarakhand

22. *Lepidospora (Lepidospora) notabilis* Silvestri, 1913

Distribution: Uttar Pradesh*

Species inquirenda (2 spp.)

Lepisma devadasi Sukumar & Livingstone, 1993

Lepisma indica Escherich, 1903

*Remarks: Mendes (1991) listed the species *Lepidospora (Lepidospora) notabilis* Silvestri, 1913 occurred from Uttar Pradesh, India. But Silvestri (1913) describe the species based on the collection from Myanmar (E. side of Dawna Hills, L. Burma).

Acknowledgements

The authors express their sincere thanks to MOEF & CC, Govt. of India, New Delhi for funding the project under AICOPTAX scheme to the Senior author. Thanks are also due to Dr. Kailash Chandra, Director, Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata for providing facilities for the present study

and to Dr. A.A. Mao Director Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata and nodal officer of the project for extending help as when required. Authors are thankful to Dr. Gautam Kundu, Principal, Vidyasagar College, Kolkata for providing the Laboratory facilities.

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